

53rd ESLAB symposium: the Gaia universe

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OPEN CLUSTER CHEMISTRY IN THE ERA OF GAIA

Focused HR spectroscopic programs

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(see extended version for full list of collaborators/institutes)

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HR spectra of OCs: what do we learn?

*a, b = Bragaglia+2018; c = Smiljanic+2018;
d = Bossini+2019; e = Cantat Gaudin+2018;
f = Soubiran+2018; g = Carrera+2019*

HR spectra of OCs: what do we learn?

As part of a wider effort involving Gaia, large surveys (Gaia-ESO, WEAVE), long-running projects (BOCCE, OCCASO) we are obtaining HRS ($R=65000-115000$ in optical, 50000 in IR) of high probability OC members, selected using Gaia DR2 :

- **SPA-OC** (*Stellar Population Astrophysics – Open Clusters*, GIARPS@TNG = HARPS-N+GIANO-B)
- **OSTTA** (*One Star to Tag Them All*, FIES@NOT)

- a few stars in a large number of nearby OCs → metallicity [abundances]
 - ages (via stellar models)
 - distribution of metallicity, abundances (chemical map of disk)
- a few ten of stars in key clusters (e.g. Praesepe, Stock 2) MS & giants → detailed abundances
 - test of stellar models (diffusion, mixing)
 - test of all nucleosynthetic chains (chemical evolution)
 - influence of activity, rotation, binarism

Legacy value : high quality sample to cross-match with large spectroscopic samples (Gaia-RVS, Gaia-ESO, APOGEE, WEAVE, etc) and with asteroseismology samples

People involved: A. Bragaglia, G. Andreuzzi, L. Balaguer-Nuñez, T. Cantat Gaudin, R. Carrera, E. Carretta, G. Casali, L. Casamiquela, G. Catanzaro, V. D'Orazi, A. Frasca, X. Fu, J. Carbajo Hijarrubia, C. Jordi, S. Lucatello, L. Magrini, D. Romano, C. Soubiran, M. Tosi, A. Vallenari

Extended on-line version

Open cluster chemistry in the era of Gaia

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Angela Bragaglia

Stellar clusters, being groups of stars sharing the same age, distance, initial chemical composition are ideal laboratories to test models of stellar and galactic formation and evolution (e.g. Freeman & Bland-Hawthorn 2002). **Gaia** observes almost the whole known population of Galactic OCs, providing crucial information on membership and high precision photometry (see e.g. Gaia Collaboration, Babusiaux et al. 2018, Cantat Gaudin et al. 2018), while the spectroscopic information (radial velocity, abundance) is more limited (Katz et al. 2019, Soubiran+2018). Ground based follow-up with higher resolution, larger spectral coverage, and reaching deeper than the Gaia RVS is then required. This has been/is/will be pursued by large surveys such as Gaia-ESO, GALAH, WEAVE, etc. A full characterization -and an accurate **age** derivation- for open clusters requires to know also the **metallicity** and possibly the full set of **detailed abundances**. Presently, less than 10% of OCs have been studied using high-resolution spectroscopy (e.g. Netopil et al. 2016, Magrini et al. 2017, Smiljanic et al. 2018), so also "private" observational programs, such as our large program **SPA** at the *TNG* with *HARPS-N+Giano-B* and the **OSTTA** project at *NOT+FIES*, are important. I will present our projects (a collaboration of researchers of INAF Bologna, Catania, Firenze, Padova; U Barcelona; U Bordeaux) and the first results. We concentrate on the brighter stars of OCs in the solar vicinity, within about 2 kpc, where Gaia precision is at its best and the membership determination is more reliable so that we can trust it also for clusters immersed in a strong contaminating field component. This permits to very efficiently observe only high-probability cluster members. Part of the OCs have been observed by Kepler, so also asteroseismologic information is available. For these OCs we will provide a detailed and accurate chemical characterization (elements of all nucleosynthetic chains, probing different formation sites) on a par with the astrometric and photometric information provided by Gaia.

SPA-OC=Stellar Population Astrophysics-Open Clusters

OSTTA=One Star to Tag Them All

Collaborations & spectrographs

SPA = Stellar Population Astrophysics (Large Program @ TNG, PI L. Origlia)

SPA-OC: Angela Bragaglia (WG coord.), Gloria Andreuzzi, Tristan Cantat Gaudin, Ricardo Carrera, Eugenio Carretta, Giada Casali, Giovanni Catanzaro, Valentina D'Orazi, Antonio Frasca, Xiaoting Fu, Sara Lucatello, Laura Magrini, Donatella Romano, Monica Tosi, Antonella Vallenari

GIARPS = HARPS-N (optical) + GIANO-B (IR)

$\lambda = 3830\text{-}6900 \text{ \AA}$, $R=115000$ + $\lambda = 0.95\text{-}2.45 \text{ \mu m}$, $R=50000$

First 3 semesters of LP done (Jun 2018 – Jan 2019)

OSTTA = One Star to Tag Them All (FIES @ NOT, PI A. Bragaglia)

Angela Bragaglia, Lola Balaguer-Nuñez, Tristan Cantat Gaudin, Ricardo Carrera, Eugenio Carretta, Giada Casali, Laia Casamiquela, Valentina D'Orazi, Xiaoting Fu, Juan Carbajo Hijarrubia, Carme Jordi, Sara Lucatello, Laura Magrini, Caroline Soubiran, Antonella Vallenari

FIES ($\lambda = 3700\text{-}8300 \text{ \AA}$, $R=67000$)

One run done (Dec 2018)

Expected output

- With SPA-OC and OSTTA (adding also independent programs such as BOCCE, e.g. Bragaglia+2018 and OCCASO, Casamiquela+2017) we will determine for the first time the metallicity of a large number of OCs. Several new OCs, discovered in Gaia DR2 (e.g. Cantat Gaudin+2018, Castro-Ginard+2018) will be especially targeted
- We provide a detailed and accurate chemical characterization of the clusters: elements of all nucleosynthetic chains, probing different nuclear reaction sites/masses in stars, thus providing robust constraints to stellar evolutionary models and to the history of the Galactic disc
- We can measure activity indicators and rotational velocities in young cluster stars (Frasca+2018)
- We can study mixing and evolutionary processes using light elements (Li, CNO, Na) and isotopes (e.g. Smiljanic+2018)
- This will be very useful to derive more robust ages of OCs (e.g. Bossini+2019)
- This will make these OCs robust test of stellar evolutionary models
- We can calibrate the $[C/N]$ ratio after dredge-up as an age indicator for field stars, providing precise and accurate $[C/N]$ at different metallicities and ages
- By studying in details the abundance patterns in both single stars and objects in multiple systems, we can test whether (and possibly how) the presence of a (close) companion affects stellar nucleosynthesis and evolution
- As a legacy, we will also perform a cross-calibration with HR large surveys and produce a key calibration for asteroseismology (age-mass-metallicity relation and asteroseismic distance scale)

Clusters observed to date

SPA-OC @ TNG

Cluster	Nr/kind stars	New
Alessi 1	5 giants	✓
ASCC 123	15 MS (A0-G2)	✓
Basel 11b	3 giants	✓
Collinder 350	2 giants	
Collinder 463	3 giants	✓
Gulliver 51	2 giants	✓
NGC 2437	7 giants	✓
NGC 2548	4 giants	✓
NGC 7044	4 giants	✓
Praesepe	5 giants, 12 MS (G)	
Ruprecht 171	4 giants	✓
Stock 2	10 giants, 19 MSTO	
Tombaugh 5	3 giants	✓

OSTTA @ NOT

Cluster	Nr. giants	New	
COIN-Gaia2	3	✓	Main targets
COIN-Gaia6	2	✓	
FSR 951	3	✓	
King 23	3	✓	
UBB 117	3	✓	
ASCC 23, NGC 581 NGC 2186	1	✓	Bright targets
NGC 1027, NGC1647, NGC 1750, NGC7654, Trumpler 2, UBB 41	2	✓	
NGC 2345, NGC 2358	3	✓	
NGC 2281	2		

*New = no [Fe/H] from HR spectroscopy
 Gulliver 51, COIN-Gaia2,6 and UBB 117, 41
 are new discoveries in GDR2*

SPA-OC clusters observed (a few examples)

Gulliver 51

NGC 2548

Selection : Gaia DR2
astrometry+photometry
(Cantat Gaudin+2018)

Only giants observed
(red clump, if present)

Stock 2

Praesepe

○ observed

Both giants and main
sequence stars observed

(note the extended MSTO in Stock 2)

First SPA-OC results. A young cluster

ASCC 123 (age=150Myr)

15 MS stars observed, spectral type A0 to G2

10 single/SB1, analyzed using ROTFIT, 5 SB2 using COMPO2
(Frasca+2018)

→ T_{eff} / $\log g$ /[Fe/H]/ $v \sin i$ /Sp.type

10 single/SB1, ATLAS9+SYNTHE

→ C,O,Na,Mg,Al,Si,S,Ca,Sc,Ti,V,Cr,Mn,Fe,Co,Ni,Cu,Zn,Sr,Y,Zr

H_{α} emission, Li abundance as age proxy

(Frasca, Catanzaro et al., in prep.)

Single/SB1: spectrum+ROTFIT template

SB2 : spectrum + simulated composite spectrum

First SPA-OC results. Four older clusters

Four old clusters : **Collinder 350, Gulliver 51, NGC 7044, Ruprecht 171**

(age=0.5 - 3.5 Gyr)

Analyzed 2, 1, 4, 4 giants, respectively, both bright giants and red clump stars

DOOp+FAMA (as in Gaia-ESO, Cantat Gaudin+2014, Magrini+2013), but using also photometric $T_{\text{eff}}/\log g$.

One star in Gulliver51 rotates too fast for analysis; bright RGB stars might be biased towards lower metallicity; tests using different approaches under evaluation; benchmark stars (with HARPS spectra, Blanco-Cuaresma+2014) analyzed as validation

(Casali, Magrini, et al. in preparation)

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